

Deliverable D4.1

Customised programme on the implementation of training skills for research infrastructure

Project Title (Grant agreement no.):	ELIXIR-STEERS: enable federated data visits and large-scale, cross-border analysis in the life sciences by users across the whole European Research Area (101131096)		
Project Acronym (EC Call):	ELIXIR-STEERS (HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01)		
WP No & Title:	WP4 - Strengthening and equipping ELIXIR Nodes and Node staff with key skills and resources in organisation, management and training		
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Deliverable Lead Beneficiary:	27. UL		
Contractual delivery date:	31/01/2026	Actual delivery date:	05/03/2026
Delayed:	Yes		
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Reviewers:	ELIXIR-STEERS Management Board (MB) members		

Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
19/12/2025	0v1	Brane Leskošek (UL), Nazeefa Fatima (UiT)	Initial version
20/02/2026	0v2	Brane Leskošek (UL), Nazeefa Fatima (UiT)	Sent to PMO after incorporating internal WP feedback
24/02/2026	0v3	Mado Fernandez (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission
05/03/2026	1v0	Mado Fernandez (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	3
2. Contribution toward project objectives	4
3. Introduction	5
3.1 Deliverable scope	5
3.2 Relationship with other Work Packages	6
3.3 Methodology applied	6
4. Description of work accomplished	7
4.1 Training Needs Assessment: Survey on Software Management Training	7
4.2 Engagement with Training Communities	8
4.3 Survey Publication and Dissemination	8
5. Results	8
5.1 Analysis and Outcomes of the Survey	8
5.2 Customised Training Programme Development and Planned Events	11
Table 1: Identified Training Needs, Existing Documentation, and Planned Training Activities per Infrastructure Component and Software Management Topic	12
6. Conclusions	13
7. Impact	14
8. Next Steps	14
9. Deviation from Description of Action	15

1. Executive Summary

The deliverable presents a customised programme to support the implementation of training skills within the framework of ELIXIR. It aims to strengthen Nodes and equip their staff with key organisational, managerial, and training competencies. It contributes to building training capacity, with a particular emphasis on software management training, and supports the broader objective of strengthening the structure, long-term development, and visibility of the infrastructure. By embedding good practices and enhancing essential skills at Node level, the programme helps create more coordinated and efficient ways of working across the organisation.

The deliverable documents the implementation of Task 4.3 and focuses on developing training capacity among Node staff in technical, training, and coordination roles. These roles are central to sharing knowledge, tools, and services with national and European user communities. Improved competencies in software management training, covering topics such as research software quality, version control, documentation, reproducibility, and FAIR-aware data practices, enhance the quality, efficiency, and reach of ELIXIR training activities. This ensures that Node staff are better prepared to design and deliver structured training programmes for software and data managers, aligned with community standards and best practices.

A core element of the work was the development of a survey to assess software management training needs from an instructor perspective. Designed through an iterative, community-informed process, it collected structured input from stakeholders across Nodes. A key milestone was the contribution to the STEERS M2.3 RSQ Indicators Implementation Hackathon, where a dedicated session on training needs helped prioritise topics in software development. This engagement ensured the survey captured both general training requirements and the specific pedagogical and technical challenges instructors face when delivering training.

Further achievements include close collaboration with the ELIXIR Training Platform, the ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer programme, and e-learning communities, as well as broad dissemination of the survey through Nodes and Training Coordinators. The resulting collection of courses, workshops, and community training events forms the core of the customised programme in software management training. The programme will be refined iteratively through feedback, follow-up analysis, and alignment with the Training Platform, ensuring activities address Node needs, build on existing resources, and develop transferable skills across the ELIXIR community. By equipping Node staff with practical knowledge and promoting collaboration, the programme also supports consistent adoption of best practices and contributes to more reproducible, high-quality research and training across the infrastructure.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
<p>Objective 1: Partner with user communities to create a toolkit for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows that allow life-scientists to benefit from open science practices in the emerging European federated data landscape. (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5)</p>	
<p>Key Result 1.1: Established partnerships with user communities that capture experiences and embed these in good practices for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows (WP2)</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Key Result 1.2: A toolkit developed consisting of guidelines, best practices and services that supports software development and recognition of individuals involved in software development (WP2, WP3)</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Key Result 1.3: Community-wide agreement on key indicators for technical, scientific, and environmental benchmarking (WP2) embedded into established software and workflow benchmarking systems (WP3)</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Key Result 1.4: Practices for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows (WP2, WP3) are adopted and embedded in ELIXIR Nodes (WP4), supporting the European federated data landscape and Horizon Europe projects</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Key Result 1.5: Demonstration of the greening potential and reduced carbon footprint of software best practice by applying toolkit and indicators in community-driven activities (WP2)</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Key Result 1.6: Stimulate engagement and uptake by users via European and national communication and outreach programmes (WP5)</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 2: Enable the landscape for cross-border data analysis in the life sciences by embedding common practice across the whole European Research Area via effective national ELIXIR Nodes. (WP4, WP5)</p>	
<p>Key Result 2.1: Build a common toolkit to enhance the operational and managerial capacity of ELIXIR Nodes that comprise all aspects of sustainability (operational excellence, business planning, interactions with industry and impact assessment) (WP4, WP5)</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Key Result 2.2: Expand the ELIXIR's Membership by transitioning candidate countries into fully operational national Nodes using capacity building actions (WP4, WP5)</p>	<p>Yes</p>

Key Result 2.3: Strengthen excellence in RI management with an ELIXIR training programme that complements established Europe-wide offerings with the infrastructure specific needs (WP4)	Yes
Key Result 2.4: Strengthen the capacity of national training programmes (WP4) to scale the dissemination, training, and uptake of the ELIXIR software development toolkit for robust, reproducible, and green software and workflows (WP5)	Yes
Key Result 2.5: Work with funders to embed the practice in data and software management plans in guidelines to grantees (WP5)	No
Objective 3: Partner in Europe and internationally for global competitiveness and sustainability. (WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Development of national SME and industry partnerships to support the European innovation ecosystem (WP5)	No
Key Result 3.2: Partnerships with other ESFRI RIs to strengthen the wider RI landscape (WP5) and support adoption of robust, reproducible, and green workflows across RI facilities.	No
Key Result 3.3: Foster global knowledge-exchange to drive good international practices and embed international partnerships in Node activities (WP5)	Yes
Key Result 3.4: Deliver a Node dissemination and communications toolkit that enables ELIXIR Nodes to amplify engagement with scientists and other stakeholders (WP5)	No

3. Introduction

3.1 Deliverable scope

This deliverable is produced within Work Package 4 (WP4), “*Strengthening and equipping ELIXIR Nodes and Node staff with key skills and resources in organisation, management and training*”, and specifically contributes to Task 4.3: Capacity building in training skills for ELIXIR Node staff. The overarching goal of WP4 is to strengthen ELIXIR Nodes in their organisational, managerial, and training capacities, thereby enabling more effective, sustainable, and visible operations across the ELIXIR infrastructure. By embedding good practices and equipping Node staff with essential skills, WP4 directly contributes to the expected outcome of a better structured and strengthened European Research Infrastructures (RI) landscape.

Within this context, the scope of this deliverable is to support the implementation of Task 4.3 by describing the approach and activities undertaken to build and consolidate training capacity among ELIXIR Node staff. The task targets staff members with technical, training, and coordination roles, recognising their key function in transferring knowledge, skills, and resources to end-users at the national and European levels. Strengthening training competencies at the Node level is expected

to increase the efficiency, reach, and quality of ELIXIR training activities, and enhance the Nodes' ability to promote their expertise and services.

The deliverable focuses on the adaptation, improvement, and deployment of training-related resources and activities, building upon existing good practices within ELIXIR and beyond. In particular, it leverages established initiatives and materials from the ELIXIR Training Platform, including the ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer (TtT) programme, as well as resources developed within individual Nodes and partner organisations. By aligning these efforts with identified Node needs and key roles defined in WP4, the deliverable contributes to a more coherent and sustainable training ecosystem across ELIXIR.

3.2 Relationship with other Work Packages

Task 4.3 and the associated deliverable are closely interconnected with other activities within WP4, notably Task 4.1 (Embedding good practices in ELIXIR Node operations) and Task 4.2 (Consolidating organisational and management capacity of ELIXIR Nodes). Together, these tasks address complementary dimensions of Node capacity building, ensuring that organisational, managerial, and training competencies evolve in a coordinated manner.

Beyond WP4, this deliverable has strong links with WP2 and WP3, particularly through the planned collocation of training activities, workshops, and hackathons. Joint events provide opportunities to exchange knowledge, align practices, and reinforce training expertise across technical, operational, and service-oriented domains. This cross-WP interaction supports the federated nature of ELIXIR by fostering collaboration between Nodes and by ensuring that training activities are well integrated with broader infrastructure development and service delivery efforts.

The deliverable is also aligned with the ongoing work programme of the ELIXIR Training Platform, ensuring consistency with ELIXIR-wide training strategies and avoiding duplication of effort. By articulating Node-level needs with platform-level planning, Task 4.3 contributes to a coordinated and sustainable approach to training capacity building across the RI.

3.3 Methodology applied

The methodology follows a structured, needs-driven, and collaborative approach, building on existing expertise and resources within ELIXIR and aligning with the ELIXIR Training Platform work programme and the overall objectives of the ELIXIR-STEERS project.

The first methodological step consisted of assessing the training needs of ELIXIR Nodes through a structured survey targeting Node staff involved in technical, training, and coordination roles. The survey focused on identifying challenges and needs related to software management training and provides the evidence base for subsequent activities, ensuring responsiveness to concrete Node-level needs and strategic priorities. To refine the survey and foster cross-WP collaboration in training capacity building, activities were co-located with WP2 and WP3 events. Workshops and exchanges were organised alongside the WP2/WP3 kick-off meeting in Padova and the ELIXIR-STEERS WP2/WP4 workshop held in conjunction with the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2025. These activities facilitated knowledge exchange, promoted alignment across work packages, and strengthened training expertise within the ELIXIR-STEERS community.

Based on the survey outcomes, a customised training programme is being developed in close collaboration with the ELIXIR Training Platform and established Train-the-Trainer (TtT) programmes. The programme combines targeted workshops, hackathons, and training events tailored to the contexts and maturity levels of participating Nodes, focusing on strengthening practical training

skills, improving training content, and embedding TtT best practices through hands-on learning and peer exchange.

In parallel, TtT courses are delivered to ELIXIR Node staff in coordination with the ELIXIR Training Platform. In addition to pedagogical principles, course design, learner engagement, and evaluation, these courses address software management training topics identified through the survey, equipping participants with transferable skills applicable across diverse training contexts.

The task is implemented through a distributed collaboration model involving multiple partners contributing complementary expertise. UiT and UL lead the task, coordinating training activities and providing organisational expertise, while partners such as SU, BioData.pt, SIB, and others contribute Train-the-Trainer knowledge, technical training expertise, and experience from established networks, including Galaxy, RDMkit, and TeSS. This approach ensures broad engagement, effective knowledge sharing, and the sustainability of training capacity-building outcomes across ELIXIR Nodes.

4. Description of work accomplished

This chapter summarises the activities, outputs, and intermediate outcomes delivered under **Task 4.3: Capacity building in training skills for ELIXIR Node staff**. The work reported here focuses on the development and implementation of a targeted training needs assessment survey, the preparation and execution of associated collaborative events, and the initial analysis and community dissemination of results. These activities serve as foundational steps for the development of a customised training programme tailored to Node needs.

4.1 Training Needs Assessment: Survey on Software Management Training

The first major work stream in Task 4.3 was the preparation of a comprehensive **survey to understand training needs from an instructor's perspective** focused on software management and related training areas. The survey was conceived as a tool to collect systematic and actionable input from ELIXIR Node staff across technical, training, and coordination roles. Its development followed an iterative, community-informed process.

The survey instrument was first mentioned and discussed during the **WP2/3 Kick-off meeting in Padova (2 - 3 Oct 2024)**, where representatives from WP2, WP3, and WP4 discussed intersecting needs in service quality and training capacity. At this event, T4.3 members gathered informal insights on tentative survey content and emerging community expectations for training support.

The survey was drafted and refined through regular WP4 and Task 4.3 meetings (since T4.3 kick-off in 22 Oct 2024), ensuring alignment with WP4 as well as WP2 and WP3 objectives and with expressed priorities in the initial project proposal. Additional substantial refinement took place during broader community discussions at the **WP4/T4.3 session at the ELIXIR General Assembly (GA) 2025 (28 - 29 Jan 2025)**, with contributions from multiple Nodes on scope, question phrasing, and the prioritisation of core competency areas.

A key milestone in survey preparation was the participation of T4.3 in the **STEERS M2.3 RSQ Indicators Implementation Hackathon (6 Jun 2025)**, co-organising a dedicated session on training

needs in parallel with the main hackathon agenda. The hackathon, designed to evaluate and implement RSQ indicators, included a focused working group on preparing a survey for software development training. This session provided an early forum to gather and prioritise training topics directly from diverse ELIXIR technical and community stakeholders. Insights from this session enriched the survey's thematic coverage and helped ensure that the instrument captured both general training needs and specific software management challenges encountered by project-aligned communities.

4.2 Engagement with Training Communities

Following internal preparation, preliminary versions of the survey were discussed with key training communities within ELIXIR, including:

- The **Train-the-Trainer (TtT) community**, where feedback centred on pedagogical priorities and competency frameworks;
- The **Training Platform (TrP) coordinators community**, which provided insights on platform-wide training priorities, modular learning pathways, and alignment with existing training resources; and
- The **e-learning community**, which contributed expertise on online learning design, assessment methods, and mechanisms to broaden participation.

These engagements informed iterative revisions of the survey instrument and contributed to its final structure and question set.

4.3 Survey Publication and Dissemination

The survey was widely published and disseminated across relevant ELIXIR channels, including:

- ELIXIR-STEERS WP2–WP4 mailing lists and collaboration platforms;
- The ELIXIR Training Platform community communication channels;
- Training-related community forums and interest groups.
- ELIXIR Tools Platform group: Software development best practices for life sciences

Dissemination was also supported through partner Node networks, extending reach to Node Training Coordinators and local training instructors including technical staff across ELIXIR. During the WP4 WPL meetings we agreed that our aim is to cover more than half of participating organisations in ELIXIR-STEERS / Nodes. The survey was open from 20 Oct 2025 until 12 Dec 2025.

5. Results

5.1 Analysis and Outcomes of the Survey

The survey captured insights from 28 instructors representing 14 distinct ELIXIR Nodes. The primary learners being taught are overwhelmingly doctoral candidates, selected by 82% (23 respondents) of trainers. While the instructors are highly experienced in their scientific and technical domains, 25% (7 respondents) currently do not have formal pedagogical training, presenting an

excellent opportunity to expand "Train-the-Trainer" programs and pedagogical upskilling to further build expertise across ELIXIR.

After the survey collection period, preliminary analysis of responses was conducted to identify key themes and priority training gaps. The results of this analysis were presented and discussed during the **ELIXIR-STEERS WP4 pre-meeting on 13 Jan 2026**, providing an opportunity for Nodes to reflect collectively on emerging priorities and to begin aligning on potential training challenges and needs.

When delivering courses, 54% (15 respondents) cited dealing with non-uniform audiences as their primary pedagogical hurdle, struggling to balance the pace for mixed-skill classrooms (Figure 2). Technically, 64% (18 respondents) voted that inconsistent learner operating systems cause the most significant disruptions during hands-on exercises (Figure 3). Beyond the classroom, long-term resource management remains a critical bottleneck, with 79% (22 respondents) reporting that a lack of time is the main barrier to keeping training materials sustainable for future reuse.

The survey data reveals a strategic shift in the community's priorities. Currently, training delivery is well-established across a broad range of core software management topics. However, when asked about future needs, software testing and version control emerged as the most desired topics for new material development (Figure 1). This indicates a strong demand for resources that help transition researchers from simply sharing code to ensuring that their software is robust, verifiable, and maintained through rigorous testing and collaborative workflows.

Despite practical time constraints, instructors/trainers demonstrate strong foundational knowledge, with 39% (11 respondents) expressing full confidence in teaching all aspects of making software FAIR. To overcome the friction of mixed-skill audiences and technical inconsistencies, 79% (22 respondents) prefer the development of "hands-on exercises" over slide decks, viewing active, self-paced modules as the most critical resource for future training success.

Following the WP4 pre-meeting, results were also shared at the **ELIXIR GA 2026 (13 - 14 Jan 2026)**, where Task 4.3 presented key findings, including priority training topics, areas of shared concern, and opportunities for integration with ELIXIR Training Platform initiatives. Feedback from these sessions has already informed the initial design of the customised training programme and continues to guide Task 4.3 planning.

Key outcomes from the survey include a prioritized list of software management training needs, stratified by Node role and context, and the identification of high-demand training topics that will shape subsequent workshops, hackathons, and Train-the-Trainer (TtT) modules. Additionally, the survey has fostered stronger alignment and a shared understanding of training priorities across ELIXIR Nodes and the broader Training communities. Together, these outputs provide the evidence base for the next phases of Task 4.3, including the detailed design and delivery of training activities in the final part of the project.

Ordered by the number of respondents wanting future materials. Bars compare current delivery vs future need. Multiple selections were allowed.

Figure 1. Current Topics vs Topics Needed for Future Software Management Training

Most frequently reported pedagogical challenges. X-axis is selections; Y-axis lists the challenges.

Figure 2. Pedagogical Challenges in Software Management Training

Figure 3. Technical Challenges in Software Management Training.

5.2 Customised Training Programme Development and Planned Events

In addition to the analysis of the training needs survey described in Section 5.1, Task 4.3 has begun to develop a customised training programme that directly responds to the priorities and gaps identified by ELIXIR Nodes. This programme builds on existing training events and initiatives offered by the ELIXIR Training Platform (TrP) and WP4 partners, and it will continue to evolve as additional activities and collaborations are confirmed.

A key output of this work is the identification and mapping of training events that serve as preparatory building blocks for the customised programme. These events contribute content, pedagogical practice, and community engagement that will be integrated into the programme design:

- **Train-the-Trainer (TtT) courses:** A series of approximately seven Train-the-Trainer (TtT) courses is planned and coordinated through the ELIXIR-GOBLET TtT community. The detailed schedule and registrations are managed by the community and will be announced via TeSS and other ELIXIR training communication channels. Delivery is distributed across Nodes and formats: planned courses include deliveries by the DE and LU Nodes (April 2026), three courses led by the CH Node (February, April and November 2026) with participation from the PT and IL Nodes, a course led by the BE Node (September 2026), a course delivered by the PT Node (2026), and additional online TtT sessions led by the SE and FI Nodes (2026). These TtT activities will strengthen core instructional competences like training design, learner engagement, and evaluation, and will be further enriched with content on software management topics identified and prioritised through the Task 4.3 needs assessment survey.
- **Training Platform (TrP) and community training events:** A range of training activities indexed in the ELIXIR Training eSupport System (TeSS) illustrate the breadth of ELIXIR-affiliated training opportunities available to Nodes and their staff. TeSS serves as a searchable registry of training events and materials, enabling the identification of relevant workshops and courses that can be integrated into, or promoted through, the customised programme to participants and stakeholders. Examples include bioinformatics, leadership, communication, and other skills relevant to ELIXIR training capacity building.

- **WP2 workshops in collaboration with WP4:** Two workshops planned in collaboration between WP2 and WP4 will contribute to training capacity building in technical and quality aspects of research software and services. One workshop is scheduled for Amsterdam in April 2026 and a second for Lyon in June as a pre-meeting to the ELIXIR AHM 2026. These events will bring together technical and training communities, reinforcing cross-work package synergies, and providing opportunities for targeted training development.
- **WP4 workshop (planned 2026):** A dedicated WP4 training workshop is being planned for late 2026, with the location to be confirmed. This workshop will consolidate insights from the survey and preceding events to shape the detailed content and delivery structure of the customised programme.

Beyond the structured activities described above, additional training needs and planned events were collected from WP2 and WP3 (see Table 1). These needs reflect thematic priorities in service quality, software sustainability, infrastructure operations, and research software engineering, and align closely with the gaps identified through the Task 4.3 survey.

To support this mapping exercise, WP4 invited members of WP2 and WP3 to contribute information on infrastructure components and software management topics relevant to their activities. Contributors were asked to indicate: (i) identified training needs, (ii) available documentation or guidance materials, and (iii) existing or planned training events addressing these areas. In addition, software management topics previously identified during the RSQ workshop held after the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2025 were included to ensure alignment with cross-WP quality and sustainability objectives.

The resulting table therefore provides a consolidated overview of infrastructure components and software management topics for which explicit documentation and/or training activities are already available or planned. Only components or topics with clearly identified materials or events are included, ensuring that the table reflects actionable and concrete training development efforts.

Several of the planned activities, including a dedicated hackathon organised by WP4 with content contributions from WP2 and WP3 software management experts, is planned to be organised as standalone events or as satellite sessions linked to major ELIXIR events such as the All Hands Meeting. This integrated approach strengthens cross-WP collaboration and ensures that technical developments and training capacity building evolve in parallel.

Table 1: Identified Training Needs, Existing Documentation, and Planned Training Activities per Infrastructure Component and Software Management Topic

Infrastructure Component and Software Management Topic	Training Needs	User guide / Documentation / Training materials (describe it or provide links)	Potential/Planned Training events (describe it or provide links + date if known)
BIP! Scholar	Train end-users on creating academic profiles that emphasize their contributions beyond traditional publications.	https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/site/help	Organise a webinar to address the described training need.

Galaxy		Many resources on the Galaxy Training Network (GTN) : https://training.galaxyproject.org/ https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/earning-pathways/fair-training.html	https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/events/2025-05-18-galaxy-academy.html
Software Management Wizard (based on DSW)	Train end-users (researchers) to create SMPs for their research software + provide feedback	https://smw.dsw.elixir-europe.org/wizard/ https://guide.ds-wizard.org/en/latest/	
WorkflowHub		https://tess.elixir-europe.org/search?q=workflowhub+	https://about.workflowhub.eu/project/events/
RO-Crate		https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/tutorials	
OpenEBench	Training on benchmarking?	https://openebench.readthedocs.io/	No trainings planned
Bioschemas		https://bioschemas.org/tutorials/community/ https://bioschemas.org/tutorials/	
Software Sustainability	WP2/3: Software Management Plans; Research Software Stories	https://elixir-steers.dsw.elixir-europe.org/ (requires login) https://everse.software/RSQLite/research_software_stories	Planned hackathons in Amsterdam (April) and at AHM.

6. Conclusions

Altogether, the collection of courses, workshops, and community training events forms the backbone of the customised training programme. The programme will be iteratively refined based on ongoing feedback, survey follow-ups, and alignment with the ELIXIR Training Platform work plan, ensuring that training activities respond to concrete Node needs, leverage existing resources, and foster transferable skills across the ELIXIR community.

7. Impact

The programme strengthens ELIXIR's training ecosystem by equipping Node staff with practical skills in software management, research software engineering, and instructional design. It enhances Node collaboration, further makes training capacity sustainable, and ensures that knowledge and best practices are disseminated widely, ultimately improving the quality and reproducibility of research across the ELIXIR network.

8. Next Steps

The work completed so far under Task 4.3 has established a solid foundation for a targeted and sustainable training capacity-building programme across ELIXIR Nodes. The training needs survey, complemented by discussions held during co-located WP2/WP3 and WP4 activities (including exchanges at the WP2/WP3 kick-off in Padova and the ELIXIR-STEERS WP2/WP4 workshop at AHM 2025), has provided a clear, evidence-based view of priority gaps and expectations related to software management training. In parallel, the structured mapping of training needs, existing documentation, and planned training events across infrastructure components and software management topics has helped identify areas where materials and expertise are already available, as well as topics that require additional development.

The next phase of Task 4.3 will therefore focus on turning these findings into coordinated training actions, while maintaining strong alignment with the ELIXIR Training Platform work programme and established Train-the-Trainer practices. This transition from assessment and planning to delivery will be implemented in a way that strengthens both (i) the ability of Node staff to design and deliver high-quality training and (ii) the availability of training content and resources that can be reused across Nodes. Particular attention will be given to ensuring that training actions are tailored to the maturity and context of participating Nodes, while still promoting harmonised approaches and shared standards across the ELIXIR network.

To maximise impact and avoid duplication, Task 4.3 will continue to leverage and connect to existing initiatives, including scheduled Train-the-Trainer courses coordinated by the ELIXIR-GOBLET community and published through TeSS and related ELIXIR training communication channels. In addition, close collaboration with WP2 and WP3 will remain a central mechanism for ensuring that technical developments, infrastructure components, and service-related practices are accompanied by appropriate training materials, guidance, and instructor capacity. Where appropriate, training activities will be embedded in or co-located with major ELIXIR events and community meetings to enable efficient participation, broaden dissemination, and strengthen connections between technical and training communities.

The following next steps will guide the continued implementation of Task 4.3:

- Prepare, Organise, Supervise that planned events happen (workshops in collaboration with WP2 - Amsterdam in April and Lyon in June and WP4 hackathon/workshop - late 2026, location TBC)

- Discuss and make operative plan for some of the collected training needs (see Table 1)

9. Deviation from Description of Action

The deadline for deliverable was at the end of January 2026 and was postponed to the end of February 2026, as the project began later than it was planned due to one staff member leaving and being replaced. There was no negative influence on milestones and deliverables for the project.

